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OPEN SCIENCE CENTER

LMU Open Science Center Impact Report 2017 – 2023

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Executive summary

By ensuring **reliability and reproducibility** of research findings, open research skills provide a fertile ground for greater **innovation, collaboration, and excellence**. International and national **fundors, governments, and stakeholders**, including **researchers** themselves, are increasingly promoting open research practices as the **new standards of good research practice**. Researchers and institutions need to be prepared for the upcoming establishment of these new norms.

The LMU Open Science Center (OSC) is a cross-disciplinary grassroots initiative that provides peer-to-peer training, builds community of practice, and conducts meta research, under the leadership of the managing director Prof. Dr. Felix Schönbrodt since 2017. This network of **90+ individual members, 12 institutional members, and 450+ community members** (mailing list subscribers) has been managed by a **full-time coordinator**, Dr. Malika Ihle, since 2022.

There is great demand for training. Since May 2022, we offered **100+h of training**, received **4500+ registrations**, often more than what we could accommodate, welcoming attendees from **16 out of 18 LMU Faculties**, from all career stages, with early-career researchers constituting the bulk of our audience. The most frequent rating of our training sessions is a **rating of 5/5**. Participants show great appreciation for the permanent accessibility of the training material (e.g. online self-paced tutorials), the practical knowledgeability of their peer instructors, and an inclusive and effective hybrid format organisation.

OSC members from various disciplines and all career stages have initiated and maintained a number of grassroots initiatives for several years such as meet-ups and reading clubs, under the umbrella and support of the OSC. Such **community building activities** are crucial to **propagate norms**.

We provide our expertise to various parties. For instance, we have provided thorough and **“extremely helpful” feedback** on the research data management sections of a number of **Cluster of Excellence applications**. We also support researchers in their implementation of specific open research practice, and often provide consultations for **other organisations** on **setting up open science initiatives or strategic plans**, making the LMU a key point of contact for adopting open science at an institutional level.

Our members published **245 peer-reviewed articles** on open science or meta-research topics, spanning **12 out of 19 fields of research**, including prestigious venues such as BMJ, Journal of Business Research, Nature Human Behaviour, Nature Machine Intelligence, Nature Medicine, PLoS Medicine, PNAS, Science. Their work also showcases how reusing open research outputs can lead to impactful new research. Finally, they are successful in securing **grants for meta-research or creating open resources** (e.g. DFG Priority Program: [META-REP](#), HORIZON MSCA Doctoral Network [SHARE-CTD](#), DFG research grant funding [VerbaAlpina](#) for 10+ years), and their team members are successful in obtaining early career **awards**.

The OSC is well embedded within a **network** of relevant **local** (e.g. University Library, Munich Center for Machine Learning, LMU-ifo Economics & Business Data Center, Digital Humanities Center, Alhub@LMU), as well as **external actors** (e.g. German Reproducibility Network, Coalition for the Advancement of Research Assessment), contributing to the visibility of the LMU and using synergy effects.

To ensure the **continuity** of the OSC, we applied for **internal grants** (LMU Excellence Frontier Fund, Fund for the Promotion of Teaching, Central Study Grant) as well as **third-party funding** (Freiraum, Volkswagen Foundation Pioneer Project). So far, we were **granted ~407.000 €**, and **could hopefully be funded an additional 550.000 €** from the Volkswagen Foundation to support our activity and coordinator until Dec 2026 (decision expected in Dec 2023). Since 2022, we also received a total of **~7.000 € institutional annual membership fees** from 2 Faculties (Business Administration and Biology) and the Department of Psychology, as well as some **payments for giving workshops outside** the LMU. These incomes cover a 0.125 FTE student assistant position and travel costs for a few guest instructors. Further incomes would allow us to scale up our offering.

Providing further funding to continue and expand our activities, our **future priorities** would include

- **strategies to multiply our capacity in teaching and community growth**; e.g. **train-the-trainer** programmes, the expansion of our **online offering of self-paced tutorials**, and a **“switch-to-open” programme** consisting in supporting individual research groups in their transition to open research workflows
- **proactively fostering meta-research collaborations** by bringing members together through **speed-networking events**.
- **offer consultations to faculty committees** to revise e.g. their recruitment criteria or curricula, and train key actors within departments, thereby **embedding open research practices within institutional practices**

Our **long-term vision**, modelled after other world-leading organisations, is to provide all researchers with continual appropriate support and modular training, by increasing the OSC’s number of staff and solidifying the OSC’s foundation, thus giving the **LMU competitive advantage in a changing international landscape** where open research practices are being established as new norms.

Peer-to-peer training	100+ hours of training	4500+ registrants from 16 of 18 Faculties	4.4/5 satisfaction rating
Community building	12 institutional members	90+ members from 12 of 18 Faculties	6 grassroots initiatives
Meta-research	245+ open science articles from 12 of 19 disciplines	DFG Priority Programme Horizon Doctoral Network DFG Individual grants	

1. Background: Open Science in a changing research landscape

"Building on the essential principles of academic freedom, research integrity and scientific excellence, open science sets a new paradigm that integrates into the scientific enterprise practices for reproducibility, transparency, sharing and collaboration resulting from the increased opening of scientific contents, tools and processes."

[UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science 2021](#)

Open research practices ensure **transparency and reproducibility** across the research lifecycle. They encompass, for example, the preregistration of studies to avoid biases, sharing data, materials, and analysis scripts to increase reproducibility, and providing the published results in an open access format to increase reach and impact. As such, these practices increase the quality and reusability of research, and therefore, provide a **fertile ground for greater innovation, collaboration, and excellence**.

The open science movement has several aims, notably to:

- Affirm the principles of the [Universal Declaration of Human Rights](#), especially those contained in Articles 19 (*"Everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers"*) and 27 (*"Everyone has the right freely to participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits."*)
- Provide **solutions to the replicability crisis / tools for the credibility revolution**. Such need was made publicly visible by large replication projects in e.g. Medicine, Psychology, and Economics which brought to light the low replicability and reproducibility of scientific findings, altering trust in science by the public and scientists themselves.
- **Benefit researchers and society** in terms of efficiency and usefulness of the scientific enterprise, by increasing the reliability of scientific findings, and facilitating collaboration and innovation.

For these reasons, there has recently been a large uptake of open science policies by governments, funders, scientific publishers, and other stakeholders across the world.

At the **governmental** level, examples include the embracement of open science by the [G7 Science and Technology Ministers](#) (2023), and by several nations e.g. [France](#), [Ireland](#), [Italy](#), [The Netherlands](#), and [Ukraine](#). In the USA, the White House declared 2023 to be [the Year of Open Science](#), to spark change and inspire open science engagement across 10 federal agencies and more than 85 universities. In Germany, open science is mentioned in the [2021 Koalitionsvertrag](#). These political shifts reflect the increased importance of opening up science to the public notably to increase its trustworthiness in society.

Research funders also aim to advance open research by changing their requirements, recommendations, and strategy. For example, in new EU-projects ([Horizon Europe](#)), immediate open access of publications is required, and research data management including the FAIRness of research data and code are required or recommended. The national research funding bodies, the German Research Foundation (DFG) and the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF),

are also increasingly focusing on open access and open data. For instance, the DFG published the position paper "[Open Science as Part of Research Culture](#)" (2022), and updated their [Code of Conduct](#) to strongly suggest the adoption of these new standards of good research practices. For instance, paragraph 13 reads: *"Providing public access to research results: [...] Where possible and reasonable, this includes making the research data, materials and information on which the results are based, as well as the methods and software used, available [...] in recognized archives and repositories in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)."*

Coalitions of **stakeholders** are also reforming ways of assessing researchers during hiring and promotion. The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment ([DORA](#)), 3,000+ organisational signatures strong, recommends moving away from using simple quantitative measures like impact factor due to its well-documented inadequacy. The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment ([CoARA](#)) works to offer alternative research assessment criteria, emphasising that *"Openness of research, and results that are verifiable and reproducible where applicable, strongly contribute to quality"*. CoARA has 650+ organisational signatures including the European Commission, the League of European Research Universities (LERU), the European University Association (EUA), the DFG, the German Psychological Association (DGPs), and the Berlin Institute of Health. At the LMU, the Department of Psychology has already changed their hiring criteria to include aspects of replicability and reproducibility.

World-leading research organisations such as the universities of [Oxford](#), [Stanford](#), [Harvard](#), [California Berkeley](#), as well as the [Massachusetts Institute of Technology \(MIT\)](#), [Imperial College London](#), and [ETH Zurich](#), all have long-term institutional open science strategies. Several **research institutions in Germany** have also adopted open science strategic plans or policies, including [Helmholtz](#), [European Molecular Biology Laboratory \(EMBL\)](#), [National Library of Economics \(ZBW\)](#), [Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg](#), [University of Konstanz](#), and [University of Mannheim](#).

To **be well prepared for the coming changes**, we need to make doctoral students, early-career researchers, and grant applicants at LMU Munich fit for open science requirements. Providing support to researchers in their adoption of open research practices more systematically through our institution will allow researchers from LMU and elsewhere to more easily **move across the international landscape** where these new norms are getting established.

2. The LMU Open Science Center

The LMU Open Science Center (OSC) was founded in 2017 as a **grassroots initiative** run by researchers for researchers, with the mission to foster open research practices across disciplines at LMU Munich and beyond. The OSC provides **peer-to-peer training** and propagates norms through **community building** activities. These lines of work are necessary for existing policies to be successfully implemented and for new infrastructure to be adopted at large scale, according to the [theory of cultural change](#).

[Prof. Dr. Felix Schönbrodt](#) is its **managing director**, and a **scientific board** is elected by OSC members. For the term 2023-2025, the scientific board includes [Prof. Dr. Niels Dingemans](#) (biology); [Dr. Sabine Hoffmann](#) (biometry); [Prof. Dr. Ralf Ludwig](#) (co-speaker, geography); [Prof. Dr. Nikolaus Plesnila](#) (co-speaker, neuroscience); [Prof. Dr. Alexander Wuttke](#) (politics). Former members of the board include [Prof. Dr. Katrin Auspurg](#) (sociology), [Prof. Dr. Ralf Elsas](#) (economics), [Dr. Julia Schulte-Cloos](#) (politics), [Prof. Dr. Anne-Laure Boulesteix](#) (statistics, medicine) and [Dr. Xenia Schmalz](#) (psychiatry).

On 27.10.2023, the OSC comprised **50 full members** (LMU professors and lecturers), **34 extraordinary members** (other researchers of the LMU such as postdocs), **7 associate members** (researchers from other research organisations who contribute to foster the goals of the OSC) spanning **12 LMU Faculties**. There were also 18 pre-doctoral students leading on open science grassroots initiatives with the OSC's support. Our [list of individual members](#) is continuously increasing.

The OSC currently has **12 institutional members** (research institutions of the LMU (e.g. departments, faculties), central institutions of the LMU (e.g. the Library), and non-LMU institutions which provide infrastructure or other services that facilitate the goals of the OSC, such as the Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ)). This includes **3 institutional members providing the OSC with yearly funds**: the Department of Psychology and the Faculty of Business Administration (since 2022), and the Faculty of Biology (since 2023). The full [list of institutional members](#) is on our website.

We also have a **community** of 460+ mailing list subscribers, and 2350+ followers combined on Twitter/X, Mastodon, LinkedIn, and Bluesky (27.10.2023). The [list of our communication channels](#) can be found on our website.

In May 2022, a full-time **coordinator**, [Dr. Malika Ihle](#), was hired through the LMU Excellence Frontier Fund. Together with the Managing Director, they meet with the scientific board once a month, suggest strategies and activities that the board approves or modifies, and organise the OSC activities and services.

This report mostly covers the OSC activities since the coordinator position started. The full timeline of the LMU Open Science Center is shown in Appendix I.

The OSC activities are organised around five areas: **1. Training, 2. Community Building, 3. Consultation, 4. Meta-Research, and 5. Liaising with Stakeholders.**

2.1. Training

We offer various **peer-to-peer trainings** including

- **lectures**, where a presenter provides usually a 1-hour educational talk,
- **workshops**, where participants learn and practise a specific skill typically over the course of 2 to 4 hours,
- **symposia**, where a group of guest presenters is invited to present impulses for discussion followed by a panel and audience discussion over the course of 2 to 4 hours,
- **train-the-trainer courses**, where future instructors are taught didactical skills to enable them to train other researchers, typically over the course of 2 days, and
- **summer schools**, where the essential package of open research practice skills and knowledge is provided to selected applicants over the course of a few days to a week.

Prior to the start of the Coordinator's position in May 2022, there have been 25 pedagogical events offered by OSC members (14 workshops, 4 lectures, 5 symposia, 2 train-the-trainer courses) for which attendance, discipline breadth, and participants' satisfaction were not systematically recorded. Since May 2022, the number of registrants, their faculty of affiliation, their satisfaction and feedback are more systematically recorded. The full [list of our training events](#) is displayed on our website.

Since 2022, the events we provide are in their vast majority offered in a **hybrid format**, with learners both online and in-person, to be as **accommodating and inclusive** as possible. Specifically, this flexibility in attendance format allows people in various circumstances to join (people with e.g. caring duties, a temporary health issue, or a disability).

Below, we provide detailed descriptive statistics about the events that took place after May 2022.

2.1.1. Number of training events and registrants

Between May 2022 and October 2023, the OSC has organised **21 pedagogical events** at the LMU (12 workshops, 4 lectures, 3 symposia, 2 summer schools (composed of a total of 20 public lectures and 15 workshops for selected applicants)) for a total of **104 hours of training**. We received a total of **4670 registrations**, including 4215 registrations for events with no seat limitations (lectures, symposia, and some workshops). For the 10 workshops with limited seats, we received 455 registrations for 275 seats available (**1.6 times more than what we could accommodate**).

In the last 2 years, we were also invited to provide lectures and **workshops outside the LMU**, e.g. for the Universities of Hamburg, Magdeburg, and Stuttgart, for a total of **18 hours**, allowing us to **generate revenue** to, in turn, invite guest instructors to the LMU and cover their expenses.

2.1.2. Evaluation of the offers

Sixteen of the training sessions offered at the LMU since May 2022 were evaluated by participants on a rating scale from 0 (*I do not recommend it*) to 5 (*I fully recommend it*). The **median rating was 5/5** (N = 201 respondents, mean = 4.4). We also asked attendees to assess the suitability of the didactic approach of each session, the level of difficulty, what they appreciated the most, and their suggestions for improvement. Across all our events, the vast majority of respondents judged the didactic approaches suitable for the content of the sessions, and the level of difficulty just right. Our most common **positive feedback** was about the quality and permanent accessibility of the training

material, the approachability and the practical knowledge of the instructors, and an inclusive and effective hybrid format organisation. Our most common negative feedback was requests for more content (e.g. field specific sessions) and more time for discussions. An example of a post-event report can be found in Appendix II (Feedback Report: Hybrid Open Science Summer School, 11.-15.09.2023).

2.1.3. Scope and reach of training opportunities

While most of our training events are targeting researchers in the quantitative sciences (e.g. medical sciences, social sciences, life sciences), we are expanding our reach and expertise into purely qualitative fields (e.g. symposium “Open Humanities: applications and limits of open science practices in the humanities” on 04.07.2023).

So far, our events had participants from **16 out of 18 LMU Faculties**. We will strive to continue to increase our reach across disciplines.

In terms of career stages, **principal investigators** (PIs), research support staff and administrators, and other stakeholders such as publishers or funders, attended almost exclusively our **symposia** (e.g. “Reforming Research Assessment: how to implement responsible procedures and move beyond impact factors and h-index?” on 13.03.2023, and “How paper mills publish fake science industrial-style - is there really a problem and how does it work?” on 20.06.2022).

Our practical **workshops** are, in contrast, attended almost exclusively by **doctoral students and postdocs**.

2.1.4. Provision of online training material

All our educational material is available online under CC-BY licences to allow reuse.

We provide [tools and resources on our website](#) to allow various actors to get a jump start with fostering open research practices, including **training material for researchers and for university teachers**, and a **dissertation agreement template** for doctoral students and their supervisors.

We also have a [repository on the Open Science Framework](#), with our workshop material (e.g. slides, recording, tutorials). For instance, the material of the Open Science Hybrid Summer School 2023 (<https://osf.io/nymr5/>) was **accessed ~ 1000 times solely on the day of advertisement**.

Finally, we provide a few self-paced tutorials on computing skills, such as on [version control](#) and [simulation of data](#), which combined, have been forked (i.e. reused) over 575 times.

Thanks to the funding of the LMU Central Study Grant (starting in 2025, see section 3.1.3.) for our **Open science Hybrid-Facilitated Self-paced Tutorials (Open-HyFaST)** project, we will drastically extend our offering of online tutorials that can be followed asynchronously, and create a landing page for all of them.

2.1.5. Further upcoming offers

Through generous funding from the Munich Center for Machine Learning (MCML), the OSC has recently established an institutional membership between LMU Munich and [The Carpentries](#)

(01.11.2023). The Carpentries is a non-profit organisation which specialises in teaching basic **Software, Data, or Library skills** to researchers of all career stages and across disciplines. As part of the membership, 15 members of the LMU will be able to access an **instructor training course** from The Carpentries. The newly trained instructors are each expected to be involved in the delivery of at least one workshop at LMU Munich within 12 months of completing the training, multiplying the number of workshops we can offer.

Finally, it is our intention (see section 3.1.5. Volkswagen Foundation Pioneer Project 2023) to provide, starting in 2024, a **“switch-to-open” program**: an innovative intervention designed to help **individual research groups** transition from closed to open and reproducible workflows. Specifically, after providing consultation to research groups, we will provide them with tailored (self)-learning resources, jointly design an optimal workflow for their research, and write a standard open research practice guide for their team that can be adapted by other research groups in their departments.

2.2. Community building

2.2.1. One university-wide hub

The members of the LMU Open Science Center have the opportunity to meet and exchange progress in their effort to promote open research practices in a **biannual members meeting**. Each new member also has the opportunity to be onboarded with a personal meeting with either the Managing Director or the Coordinator, and is surveyed for their interests in order to create future **matchmaking networking events**. Members of the OSC collaborate to write opinion pieces and conduct meta-research projects (see section 2.4. Meta-research).

2.2.2. Several decentralised initiatives

Within the LMU Open Science Center, several smaller grassroots initiatives have been created by senior researchers, early-career researchers, and/or students, to meet the needs of their specific sub-communities. The OSC provides them with logistical and conceptual support, and guidance on community building and maintenance.

The **Open Science Initiative in Psychology**, led by early-career researchers including **Dr. Stefan**, invites guest presenters and provides, each semester, advanced open science workshops that are specific to their discipline.

The **Open Science Initiative in Medicine** is a group of professors and staff (including **Profs. Drs. Plesnila** and **Boulesteix**) who offers specialised workshops yearly and meet monthly with an invited group of internal stakeholders (e.g. animal welfare officers, graduate programme coordinators, faculty representatives) in order to decide on a set of strategic actions that can be taken to promote the adoption of open research practices within the Faculty of Medicine.

The **Open Science Initiative in Statistics** is a group of early-career researchers chaired by **Dr. Herrmann**, who collaborate to provide courses and seminars and co-create guidance on best practices for their department.

The **ReproducibiliTea Journal Club** is led by a group of bachelor and doctoral students to offer space, twice a month, for open discussions on open and reproducible science, and is welcoming participants from all academic levels and disciplines to foster a rich and diverse exchange of ideas.

The **RPsyche** meetup is led by bachelor students in psychology to provide space, weekly, for discussing and implementing bite-size programming skills in the R language.

The **Hacky Hour** is a monthly meetup that will start in 2024, where researchers will be able to share tips and resolve issues around the use of tools for computational reproducibility in a social environment.

2.2.3. Stipends to further community building

In 2023, we offered 3 stipends (2 x 250 euros and 1 x 500 euros) to three early-career researchers of various disciplines (linguistics, biology, and statistics) to attend an open science retreat during which they worked on fostering an open science initiative at the LMU. They presented their ideas and progress during the following OSC members' meeting and we are currently working on implementing them.

2.3. Consulting

2.3.1. Clusters of Excellence

In the 2024 round of applications for Clusters of Excellence, the DFG provided new guidelines which emphasise good research data management and data sharing practices; these topics are at the core of our expertise. In December 2022, the LMU Research Strategy Unit invited the OSC to **present our services to the coordinators of existing Clusters**.

We then provided **support for the (new or renewing) Cluster of Excellence's applicants** who reached out to us during the stage of pre-proposal submission. We provided them with thorough feedback on their research data management section, informing them of the current best standards of practice, as observed in other Clusters of Excellence in Germany or prestigious centres in Europe. We recommended procedures that we thought would both meet the DFG's expectations and be practically implementable into researchers' workflows, while being beneficial for them.

Prof. Dr. Kutyniok, spokesperson of a Cluster of Excellence application commented on the process: "The Open Science Center was **extremely helpful** for us to complete the section on Research Data Management in our pre-proposal. In fact, without them we would have not been able to write this part in such a comprehensive manner as it was possible with their **amazing support**."

We will make ourselves available again to applicants entering the second stage of application in 2024.

2.3.2. Researchers

We regularly receive requests for support over email, LMU chat, or brief Zoom calls, which we have not been keeping track of given their frequency and their rather informal nature.

LMU researchers reach out with questions on e.g.:

- the **implementation practicalities** of specific open research practices, e.g. feedback on the level of details in a preregistration in a field where the practice isn't common yet, or on how to integrate a computing skill to increase reproducibility and facilitate collaboration with their peers
- our **knowledge and experience** with suitable research infrastructures, or on how to deal with copyrights and open licences
- **where to find help** for specific questions. We have listed [LMU units that can provide specialised help](#) on our website to improve the information flow across several LMU units and to facilitate answering such questions.

2.3.3. Other universities

The LMU Open Science Center has been **contacted by members of several institutions** to provide advice on setting up institutional open science strategic plans or open science grassroots initiatives, making the LMU a key point of contact for adopting open science in a German university. Researchers or research administrators who requested our support were from institutions that include the Universities of Giessen, Lübeck, Mainz, Mannheim, Münster, Saarbrücken, and Witten-Herdecke.

2.4. Meta-research by OSC members

Members of the LMU Open Science Center **collaborate** to publish **peer-reviewed research** and to apply for **grants**. Their work also demonstrates that sharing and **reusing open research resources** can lead to impactful work that is sometimes officially recognised through **awards**.

2.4.1. Peer-reviewed articles

Members of the OSC have written **245 articles** on **open science topics, meta-research, or describing open resources such as open datasets and software**, spanning **12 out of 19 fields of research**. The complete list (as of 15.11.2023) can be found in Annex III .

Examples of high profile articles are:

- **Auspurg K. & Brüderl J.** (2022) How to Increase Reproducibility and Credibility of Sociological Research. In: "*Handbook of Sociological Science. Contributions to Rigorous Sociology*" edited by Klarita Gërxhani, Nan Dirk de Graaf and Werner Raub, **Edward Elgar Publishing Ltd.**, 512-527.
- Vasey B, ..., **Boulesteix A**, et al. (2022). Reporting guideline for the early-stage clinical evaluation of decision support systems driven by artificial intelligence: DECIDE-AI. **Nature Medicine**. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-022-01772-9>
- Mills J, ..., **Dingemans N**, et al. (2015). Archiving primary data: solutions for long-term studies. **Trends in Ecology and Evolution**. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2015.07.006>
- Naudet F, ..., **Hoffmann S.** (in press) Improving the transparency, reliability and accountability of observational studies through registration. **BMJ**.

- Camerer C, ..., **Imai T**, et al. (2016). Evaluating replicability of laboratory experiments in economics. *Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaf0918>
- O’Dea R, ..., **Ihle M**, ..., Nakagawa S (2021). Towards open, reliable, and transparent ecology and evolutionary biology. *BMC Biology*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12915-021-01006-3>
- **Mansmann U**, et al. (2023) Implementing clinical trial data sharing requires training a new generation of biomedical researchers. *Nature Medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-022-02080-y>
- Naudet F, ..., **Mansmann U**, ..., Ioannidis J (2021). Medical journal requirements for clinical trial data sharing: ripe for improvement. *PLOS Medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1003844>
- Littmann M, ..., **Sorbie A**, ..., Rost B (2020). Validity of machine learning in biology and medicine increased through collaborations across fields of expertise. *Nature Machine Intelligence*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0139-8>
- **Sarstedt M** & Adler SJ. (2023) An advanced method to streamline *p*-hacking. *Journal of Business Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2023.113942>
- **Schönbrodt F** (2019). Training students for the open science future. *Nature Human Behaviour*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-019-0726-z>
- Nosek B, ..., **Schönbrodt F** & Vazire S (2022). Replicability, robustness, and reproducibility in psychological science. *Annual Review of Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-020821-114157>
- Breznau N, Rinke EM, **Wuttke A**, et al. (2022) Observing many researchers using the same data and hypothesis reveals a hidden universe of uncertainty. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2203150119>

2.4.2. Successful reuse of open resources

Sharing or reusing open research resources can also lead to high profile work in practice.

Examples include:

- **Auspurg, K.**, & **Brüderl, J.** (2021) Has the Credibility of the Social Sciences Been Credibly Destroyed? Reanalyzing the “Many Analysts, One Data Set” Project. *Socius*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23780231211024421>
 - This paper is **reusing data and analyses a many-analyst project**, i.e. it is **meta-meta-research**. Cited 47 times on Google Scholar (30.10.2023)
- Probst P, Wright MN, **Boulesteix A-L.** (2019) Hyperparameters and tuning strategies for random forest. *WIREs Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/widm.1301>

- A paper presenting a benchmark study **based on open data** from the “openML” platform **and a freely available package** called “tuneRanger”; cited 1181 times on Google Scholar (30.10.2023)
- **Herrmann M**, Probst P, Hornung R, Jurinovic V, **Boulesteix A-L**. (2021) Large-scale benchmark study of survival prediction methods using multi-omics data. *Briefings in Bioinformatics*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbaa167>
 - A benchmark study **based on open data from The Cancer Genome Atlas**; cited 59 times on Google Scholar (30.10.2023)
- **Jimenez-Soto LF** (2016) Trans-Blot® Turbo™ Transfer with Home-made buffers [dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.ghhbt36](https://doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.ghhbt36)
 - This protocol, along with the 7 other protocols Dr. Jimenez-Soto shared on protocol.io, have been **viewed 17800+ times**, exported 490+ times, bookmarked 20+ times, **forked (i.e. copied to include modifications and republished) 10+ times**, and followed through and confirmed as working as intended by other researchers 10+ times (02.11.2023).
- **Krefeld T & Lücke S**. (Hrsg.) (2014–): VerbaAlpina. Der alpine Kulturraum im Spiegel seiner Mehrsprachigkeit, München, online, <https://dx.doi.org/10.5282/verba-alpina>
 - This project **reuses many open dictionaries and linguistic atlases**, to combine them into an enriched and interactive online platform. This way of publishing merges lexicography, cartography and scientific discourse. The project is **visited by around 600 unique individuals per month** (Oct 2023).

2.4.3. Awards

Practising **open research** or conducting **meta-research** also leads to **recognition** by several societies:

PhD students from OSC members **Prof. Dr. Auspurg** and **Dr. Schneck** received the European Research Association **Early Career Award** 2023 for their article:

- Krähmer D, Schächtele L, Schneck A (2023) Care to share? Experimental evidence on code sharing behavior in the social sciences. *PLOS ONE*. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0289380>

Team members of **Prof. Dr. Boulesteix** received several **awards for their meta-scientific work**.

- Julian Lange: Young Statistician Award, CEN conference 2023
- Julian Lange: GMDS best master's thesis award in medical biometry, 2023
- Theresa Ullmann GMDS best dissertation award in medical biometry, 2023
- Theresa Ullmann: Best poster award at International Biometric Conference 2022
- Christina Nießl: Young Statistician Award, Biometrical Colloquium 2021

Prof. Dr. Schönbrodt received the [Psychology Advancement Award for Quality Assurance](#) in 2022 for his highly committed theoretical and solution-oriented work and his commitment to anchoring the topic of open science in research practice and in the training of young scientists.

2.4.4. Grants

Members of the LMU Open Science Center have obtained **large grants to further research on open science practices or meta-research.**

Prof. Drs. Gollwitzer, Auspurg, and Schönbrodt collaborated to obtain a **DFG Priority Program: [A meta-scientific program to analyze and optimize replicability in the behavioral, social, and cognitive sciences \(META-REP\)](#)** with an overall funding volume of **5.200.000 €** in 2022.

As part of the DFG Priority Program META-REP, four more projects led by OSC members were funded for (initially) three years, acquired by **Prof. Dr. Auspurg** and **Dr. Schneck** (“Enhancing the Robustness of Observational Social Science Research by Computational Multi-Model Analyses”, **400.715 €**), **Prof. Dr. Heene** (“Explaining Heterogeneity in Direct Replications: Just Methodological Artefacts?”, **236.300 €**), **Prof. Dr. Haim** (“What Defines and Affects Replicability in Computational Communication Science?”, **189,450 €**) and **Prof. Dr. Schönbrodt** (“How an academic system can achieve a trustworthy knowledge base: Analyzing reform proposals in an agent-based modeling approach”, **277.000 €**). **Dr. Schneck** and team members further secured treasure box funding for sub-projects.

Prof. Dr. Mansmann coordinates the **HORIZON Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Doctoral Network** programme: [Sharing and Re-using clinical trial data to maximise impact \(SHARE-CTD\)](#). This doctoral network involves 9 PIs and further 12 academic and non-academic partners, and will fund 11 PhD students starting in Autumn 2024, with an overall funding of **3.000.000 €**.

Prof. Dr. Boulesteix obtained **three DFG individual grants** for **meta-scientific research** projects: “Empirical studies on the researchers degrees of freedom in biomedical data analysis” funding one TVL 13 position through 2020-2023; “Towards neutral comparison studies in methodological biostatistics research” funding one TVL 13 position through 2021-2024 ; “Empirical studies on the researchers degrees of freedom in biomedical data analysis” which will fund one TVL 13 position through 2024-2027.

Several LMU members, including OSC member **Dr. Imai** are involved in a large project called [Lab²](#) coordinated by **WZB Berlin Social Science Center** on replication and meta-science, which is now funded by the **Leibniz association**.

Prof. Dr. Krefeld and **Dr. Lücke** have been funded by the **DFG from 2014 to 2023** to edit the online resource VerbaAlpina: Der alpine Kulturraum im Spiegel seiner Mehrsprachigkeit, <https://dx.doi.org/10.5282/verba-alpina>

OSC members also obtained **small grants** to allow **peer-to-peer training** and **community building**, for instance:

- **Prof. Dr. Schönbrodt** and **Dr. Stefan** got a **small Training Grant** (3.500€) from the EU consortium “Fostering Improved Training Tools For Responsible Research & Innovation (Fit4RRI)” to organise an open science workshop.
- **Prof. Dr. Schönbrodt** obtained a catalyst award (5.200€) from the Berkeley Initiative for Transparency in the Social Sciences (BITSS) to create an open science curriculum reusable by all graduate schools.

- **Prof. Dr. Wuttke** obtained a catalyst award (5.200€) from the Berkeley Initiative for Transparency in the Social Sciences (BITSS) to conduct a pre-registered adversarial collaboration on the question of whether freedom of speech is in danger on university campuses.

2.5. Liaison with stakeholders

The LMU Open Science Center strives to network with relevant actors at the university, regional, national and international level in order to support the visibility of the LMU and to use synergy effects.

2.5.1. Internal stakeholders

We collaborate with the **Research Data Management help desk of the University Library** to provide complementary training. For instance, we ran several introductory sessions to open data (e.g. during the open data week 2023), and contribute to each other's line ups of presenters at each other's larger events or series of events (e.g. their team introduced research data management plans during the OSC summer school 2023 and we presented the Open Science Framework during the University Library Coffee Lectures series 2023).

The **University Library** is also, as a whole, an institutional member of the OSC, supporting us in kind (e.g. providing our venue for the OSC summer school 2023).

We exchange monthly with the **Research Funding Unit** to discuss new funders' requirements and opportunities to further promote open research practices at the LMU. We refer to each other's services to researchers in need of support (e.g. the Research Funding unit describes the OSC in the factsheets they provide to researchers applying for specific funding schemes), and we offer workshops conjointly (e.g. "Introduction to open data and funders requirements").

We stay in touch with the **Research Strategy Unit** to make ourselves available to Clusters of Excellence's applicants.

We liaise with the **Graduate Center** to provide complementary training on research methodology and we contributed to a good research practices Moodle course covering e.g. misconduct and plagiarism. Extending and upgrading this course to include the current standards of good research practices could be a possible venue to start institutionalising open research practices and offering an online modular course for all students and staff at the LMU (see section 4. Future strategies).

Graduate programme coordinators, such as the ones from the Graduate School of Systemic Neurosciences, the Munich Medical Research School, the Medical Research in Epidemiology and Public Health, recommend our training to their graduate students and provide them with ECTS for their attendance.

If our Volkswagen Foundation application is granted (see section 3.1.5.), we will collaborate with the **Center for Leadership and People Management** to include leadership skill training in our open science train-the-trainer programme so trainers can become successful managers of change.

The **Munich Center for Machine Learning** funded the establishment of an institutional membership between the LMU and The Carpentries, a non-profit organisation which specialises in teaching basic

Software, Data, or Library skills to researchers. The platinum membership (15.000 USD) will be managed by the OSC Coordinator and the MCML Open Science Transfer Coordinator, and allow us to train 15 new instructors, who will subsequently teach workshops to our communities.

The LMU Open Science Center is a founding member of the **Alhub@LMU** launched in October 2023. This interdisciplinary platform is dedicated to enhancing AI and Data Science research across our University and brings researchers together to shape and prepare the future digital society.

The **LMU-ifo Economics & Business Data Center (EDBC)** is an institutional member of the OSC, and an accredited research data centre, where local and visiting researchers have the possibility to work in a secure, well-equipped and supervised environment with sensitive, access-restricted data sets. The EDBC team, headed by OSC member **Dr. Wichert**, offers guidance on good research data management practices.

The **Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ)** is also an institutional member of the OSC and supports us by providing infrastructures related to open science practices and training on their appropriate use.

The **Digital Humanities Center (ITG)** is another institutional member of the OSC who provides support to researchers in the Humanities. We co-organised a symposium with them and the Research Data Management helpdesk of the University Library to start conversations with humanities researchers on the applications and limits of open science practices in their field of research.

We take part in each National Research Data Infrastructure general meeting taking place at the LMU, **NFDI@LMU**, and contribute short presentations and expertise to these meetings.

Finally, we are liaising with the **Munich Postdoc Network**, and provide e.g. lectures for them during the National Postdoc Appreciation Week.

2.5.2. External stakeholders

The LMU Open Science Center is a **co-founder of the [German Reproducibility Network](#)**, a national cross-disciplinary consortium that aims to increase trustworthiness and transparency of scientific research. The OSC Managing Director was a member of the steering committee (2020-2023), and the OSC Coordinator has been the GRN Local Network Lead at LMU Munich since 2022. The network organises training and community building activities, which have resulted in articles such as

- Rahal RM, ..., **Schönbrodt F**, ..., Azevedo F. (2023). Quality research needs good working conditions. *Nature Human Behavior*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-022-01508-2>
- Kohrs FE, ..., **Ihle M**, ..., Weissgerber TL. (2023). Eleven Strategies for Making Reproducible Research and Open Science Training the Norm at Research Institutions. *eLife* <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.89736>

The OSC Managing Director is also the speaker of the Open Science / Data Management commission of the **German Psychological Society (DGPs)**, and co-lead of the Working Group “Responsible Metrics and Indicators” in the **Coalition for the Advancement of Research Assessment (CoARA)**. He shaped the [DGPs recommendations for a transparent data management](#), and proposed practical implementation of responsible research assessment, published in

- **Schönbrodt F**, et al. (2022 preprint, in press in *Meta-Psychology*). Responsible Research Assessment I: Implementing DORA for hiring and promotion in psychology. <https://doi.org/10.23668/psycharchives.8162>
- Gärtner A, Leising D, **Schönbrodt F**. (2022 preprint, in press in *Meta-Psychology*). Responsible Research Assessment II: A specific proposal for hiring and promotion in psychology. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/5yexm>
- Gärtner A, Leising D, **Schönbrodt F**. (2023). Empfehlungen zur Bewertung wissenschaftlicher Leistungen bei Berufungsverfahren in der Psychologie. *Psychologische Rundschau*. <https://doi.org/10.1026/0033-3042/a000630>

NASA and **CERN** organised an open science policy summit in Geneva in 2023 in which the OSC Coordinator participated. The [closing statement](#) (“Sowing the Seeds of Global Open Science Coordination”) includes concrete commitments on how the transition to a more open, equitable, robust, and sustainable research ecosystem can be accelerated. The OSC Coordinator is taking part in the [working groups](#) formed to materialise a worldwide coordination on open science policy.

The OSC Managing Director is an advisory board member of the **Open Science Office of the University of Mannheim** since 2021 and a scientific board member of the **Leibniz Institute for Psychology** (which describes itself as a “public open science institute”) since 2017.

The OSC was consulted by the LMU Research Funding Unit in charge of the **Open Science Task of EUGLOH** in 2023. We are also exchanging with the **LERU** and **UNESCO Open Science Working Groups** since 2022 and collaborate with the **U15** (e.g. on their statement on the BMBF “Konsultation zum Forschungsdatengesetz”).

Finally, we were reviewers for the **ZBW – Leibniz Information Centre for Economics** Open Science Conference 2023 and the OSC Coordinator was interviewed for the ZBW Open Science Magazine about the didactical aspect of the OSC Hybrid Summer School 2023 funded by the LMU Fund for the Promotion of Teaching 2022.

3. Financial sustainability

The LMU Open Science Center, and particularly the coordinator's position, is largely funded by internal grants. We are also applying for third-party funding to ensure the position's continuity.

3.1. Grant applications

3.1.1. LMU Excellence Frontiers Fund 2021 ✓

The OSC applied for and was granted 250.000,00 € to cover a coordinator's position between 01.05.2022 - 31.12.2024 in order to scale up and professionalise the OSC's activities.

3.1.2. LMU Fund for the Promotion of Teaching 2022 ✓

We presented the project "**Hybrid Open Science Summer School 2023**" to implement lessons learned from the pandemic in terms of new didactic approaches and were granted 15.320,15 €. The summer school was very successful (see Appendix II: "Feedback Report: Hybrid Open Science Summer School, 11.-15.09.2023") and lessons learned about didactics were shared through an [interview with the ZBW Open Science Magazine](#).

3.1.3. LMU Central Study Grant 2023 ✓

We applied to fund the development of self-paced tutorials on open research that can be facilitated at large scale in a hybrid format or "**Open science Hybrid-Facilitated Self-paced Tutorials (Open-HyFaST)**", and will be granted 141.490,00 € to cover the Coordinator's salary from 01.01.2025 to 31.12.2025 and commission training developers.

3.1.4. Freiraum 2023 ⊗

We applied with the concept of Open science Hybrid-Facilitated Self-paced Tutorials (Open-HyFaST) for 150.330,00 € which was declined in the second round of application.

3.1.5. Volkswagen Foundation Pioneer Project 2023 ?

We applied for the call "Pioneer Projects - Impetus for the German Research System" with a project entitled "**From local to systemic implementation: Embedding open research in institutional practices**" composed of two work packages: (i) a "**switch-to-open**" program, an innovative intervention designed to help individual research groups transition from closed to open workflows, (ii) a complementary **train-the-trainer program** focusing on empowering participants to become instructors of open research practices to increase uptake within their disciplines. The budget applied for is 550.000,00 € and would cover the current coordinator position until 31.12.2026, a second coordinator position from 01.01.2024 to 31.12.2026, and other project costs. We reached the second round of selection and expect a final reply in December 2023.

3.2. Incomes and expenditure

The maintenance of the OSC services are largely dependent on the funding of the coordinator's position and of additional funding to cover expenses for inviting guest instructors and other basic costs.

The **Frontiers LMU Excellence 2021** covers the current **Coordinator's salary** (01.05.2022 - 31.12.2024) and the **LMU Fund for the Promotion of Teaching 2022** allowed us to conduct a **week-long hybrid summer school in 2023** (covering student assistants salaries, honoraria and travel expenses for external guest presenters, and some technical equipment to allow the hybrid format).

3.2.1. Membership from funding institutional members

Three LMU research units (Department of **Psychology**, Faculty of **Business Administration**, Faculty of **Biology**) are providing us with yearly funds for a total of **~7.000 euros per year** from 2022. This typically covers

- **student assistant** salary of ~5.000 euros per year
- **travel expenses for guest instructors** ~1.000 euros per year
- electronic and stationary material ~500 euros per year
- travel costs for the coordinator ~300 euros per year
- server maintenance ~200 euros per year

We hope to recruit more funding institutional members to scale up our offers by hiring more student assistants and cover the travel expenses of more guest instructors.

3.2.2. External income

Once a semester, we accept one of several **external invitations to give a workshop**. Since 2022, we have earned on average **1.500 euros per year** this way to give workshops in e.g. the Universities of Stuttgart, Hamburg, and Magdeburg.

We used this fund to invite **additional guest instructors to the LMU** and cover their travel expenses and possible honoraria.

We receive more demand than what we typically offer, but we have limited capacity to increase our teaching time outside of the LMU.

4. Future strategies

Providing further internal and/or third-party funding, we will maintain and expand our services.

4.1. Multipliers of training capacity and community growth

While we want to continue delivering our training and community building offers given their great reception and the urgent needs of researchers, we also need to develop **strategies to multiply our capacity in teaching** given the ever-increasing demand.

For this, we started a membership with the Carpentries to **train instructors of computing skills**, who will in turn run their own workshops (see section 2.1.5. Further upcoming offers).

We will also scale-up our offering of **online self-paced tutorials** that can be followed asynchronously thanks to the funding of the LMU Central Study Grant (starting in 2025, see section 3.1.3.).

In addition, we applied for a Volkswagen Foundation grant to deliver a fully rounded **open science train-the-trainer programme** (including open science, didactics, and leadership skill training). Within the same application, an additional coordinator position was requested to run a **“switch-to-open” programme** consisting of supporting individual research groups in their transition to completely open research workflows. If funded, we would consult research groups, provide them with tailored (self)-learning resources, design together an optimal workflow for their research, and write a standard open research practice guide for their team that can be adapted by other research groups in their departments. Thanks to both programmes, we expect both passive and active dissemination of practices within departments, thereby initiating systemic change (Figure 1).

Finally, if the OSC increases its number of staff and its financial stability, we hope to develop a good research practices **Moodle course** up to current standards as this could be a way to **scale up and offer a basic online training for all students and staff at the LMU**. Some Universities already offer (e.g. [University College London](#)) or are developing (e.g. University of Oxford) such training which they (will) recommend or mandate during the onboarding of new students and/or staff.

Figure 1. **Local nucleus of change.**

Within each department, our “switch-to-open” programme will support a research group to become a model for their peers, by developing a written standard open research practice guide that can be adopted or adapted by other research groups. This programme will raise awareness of open research practices (ORPs) and lead to passive dissemination of knowledge to other working groups. In addition, trained instructors from our train-the-trainer programme (which may or may not be members of the switched groups) will pass on skills to their peers, actively disseminating new practices within their department. Combined, these efforts will embed ORPs locally, and change local culture within each department, thereby initiating systemic change.

4.2. Provision of further meta-research collaboration opportunities

So far, collaborations between OSC members happened organically, for example when meeting or contacting each other due to their common (open or meta-) research interests. We intend to **more actively foster collaboration** for meta-research projects by bringing members together through a **match making** survey and algorithm. We plan to organise group **speed-networking events** and **one-one networking lunches** starting from 2024. This way, we will provide many more opportunities for collaborations, make better use of possible synergies, and provide numerous incubation spaces for new meta-research projects.

4.3. Institutionalisation of open research practices

Through the Volkswagen Foundation project (if funded), notably, the train-the-trainer and switch-to-open programmes, we will work to further embed open research practices within institutional practices by **training key people within departments**. They will, in turn, have the ability to e.g. adjust curricula offered or recruitment criteria used in their unit. We will also proactively **offer consultations to faculty committees** that wish to formalise a strategic plan for open research within their unit, e.g. by embedding systematic **training in official curricula**, revising their **incentives, recommendations and/or policies**.

4.4. Formation of an advisory board

We are in the process of inviting key internal and external advisors to be part of our advisory board so we can **benefit from their feedback and experience**.

The following invitees already **accepted to become our advisors** (01.12.2023):

- **Prof. Dr. Stephan Hartmann** (Dean of the Faculty of Philosophy, LMU Munich)
- **Dr. Bernhard Goodwin** (Executive Director of the Munich Science Communication Lab, LMU Munich)
- **Dr. Tanita Casci** (Research Strategy & Policy Unit Director, University of Oxford)
- **Prof. Dr. Ulrich Dirnagl** (Founding Director of the QUEST Center for Responsible Research, Berlin Institute of Health)

Annex I - LMU Open Science Center timeline

Foundation of the Open Science Initiative in Psychology	Jul 2015
The Department of Psychology incorporates an open science statement into all professorship job announcements.	Dec 2015
Foundation of the LMU Open Science Center	Nov 2017
Onboarding of OSC Institutional Members <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ) - University Library - Faculty of Medicine - Faculty of Veterinary Medicine - Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences - Department Psychology (Funding Institutional Member from 2022) - Department of Statistics - LMU-ifo Economics & Business Data Center (EBDC) - Munich Center for Neurosciences - Digital Humanities Center (ITG) 	2018/2019
Foundation of the Open Science Initiative in Medicine	Jan 2019
The Department of Psychology requires all Ph.D. students and their primary supervisor to draft an open science dissertation agreement.	Nov 2019
Foundation of the Reproducibilitea Journal Club	Dec 2019
Foundation of the Open Science Initiative in Statistics	Jun 2021
Start of a full-time coordinator position	May 2022
The OSC becomes an Institutional Member of the German Reproducibility Network	Oct 2022
Onboarding of OSC Institutional Members <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Faculty of Business administration (Funding Institutional Member) - Faculty Biology (Funding Institutional Member) 	2022/2023

Annex II - Feedback report: Hybrid Open Science Summer School, 11.-15.09.2023

Programme and abstracts: <https://malikaihle.github.io/OSC-Open-Research-Summer-School-2023/>

Descriptive statistics

Full participants (lectures + workshops)

We requested researchers/students interested in attending both the lectures and the workshops to apply. We received **95 applications** (58% of which LMU members).

We **selected 35** (of which 68% from the LMU). They were PhD students (16), MSc Students (12), post docs or junior PIs (7); 18 men and 17 women. Disciplines included Medicine, Biology, Psychology, Social sciences, Business Administration, Statistics, Epidemiology, Geosciences. Our selected participants were joining from the following countries: Germany (27), Australia (1), Canada (1), Czechia (1), Denmark (1), India (1), Mexico (1), Nigeria (1), Portugal (1).

Thirty-three persons actually attended the whole course (16 in person, 9 online, 8 with mixed-format attendance).

Public participants (lectures)

The lectures were advertised publicly for online attendance. A total of **312 registrants** (30% of which being LMU members) registered for one or more lectures. Each lecture received on average 197 registrations (range: 160-312) and were attended by 46 people (range 31-74) in addition to the full-course attendants.

Julia public participants (Julia workshop)

The Julia programming workshop was opened to public registrations and capped at **40 seats** including the 18 summer school participants having chosen that session out of two parallel workshops. We received **39 additional public registrations** (62% of which from the LMU, including the waiting list). A total of 33 people attended (20 online (public participants) and 13 in person (summer school participants)).

Material

We shared all our **material** on the OSF repository: <https://osf.io/nymr5/> which was **visited ~1000 times on 18.09.2023 alone** (the day the material was advertised).

Feedback survey

We received **21 responses from full-course participants** (64%), including 10 in-person attendees, 3 online attendees, and 8 mixed-format attendees.

We received an additional **21 responses from online participants of the public lectures**, and an additional **5 responses from public participants of the Julia workshop**.

Session rating

Each of the 25 sessions was rated from 0 (*I do not recommend it*) to 5 (*I fully recommend it*). Overall, on average, the sessions were rated 4.3 (min = 0, max = 5, **median =4**).

There is not much difference in satisfaction across the attendance format, though the mixed-format attendees had the lowest satisfaction.

<u>attendance format</u>	<u>n</u>	<u>mean</u>	<u>min</u>	<u>max</u>	<u>median</u>
in-person	10	4.27	2	5	5
online	3	4.55	1	5	5
mixed	8	3.98	0	5	4

Suitability of the workshops formats for the content to be delivered

For each of the 9 workshops, we asked: "Do you think the training methods applied in the workshops, e.g. workshop format or exercises, were appropriate for the respective workshop content?". We had a mix of workshop formats, e.g. either full walk through from the instructor, walk through from the instructor incorporating regular mini-exercises, or fully self-paced tutorials with facilitators present.

Out of 149 ratings, **117 (79%) indicated a suitable format for the content**, 27 (18%) indicated undecided, and 5 (3%) indicated the format was unsuitable.

Comments associated to this question were:

- [1] "in general yes, but some more interactive parts in self-paced tutorials would have been nice."
- [2] "Preregistration could have been shown in practice, additionally to explaining it theoretically. I really liked most workshops, especially the GitHub workshop and basically all self-paced stuff"
- [3] "I think more engaging workshops with doing exercises together and discussing rather than just following tutorial would be more helpful and teaching."

Level of the workshop

The summer school was targeted at novices in open research practices. It welcomed early career researchers from various disciplines and with diverse prior knowledge.

Overall, across all workshops, 67 scores indicated participants had *no prior knowledge* of the topic, 55 *basic prior knowledge*, 33 *advanced prior knowledge*, 5 *expert prior knowledge*.

Overall, across all workshops, **104 (74.3 %)** judged the difficulty level of the content to be **just right**, 25 thought it was *too easy*, 7 *much too easy*, 4 thought it was *too difficult* and 0 thought it was *much too difficult*.

Overall, we expected participants with increasing prior knowledge to find our training material increasingly easy as it is primarily targeted at novices, but the vast majority found the level *just right*, across prior knowledge levels.

Gains from the summer school

We asked: "Overall, did you gain any of the following attending this Summer School?", offering a list of options.

21 full-participants answered that question, and an additional 21 participants of the public lectures.

<u>Gains</u>	<u>% full participants</u>	<u>% public participants</u>
New insight/understanding	95.2	38.1
New skills	100	85.7
Support network/sense of community	71.4	19
Inspiration/Empowerment/Motivation to adopt open research practices in your work	100	66.7
Inspiration/Empowerment/Motivation to become an ambassador for open research practices	61.9	47.6
None of the above	0	4.8
Other, please specify:	4.8	0

Other gains indicated by the respondents were:

[1] "A good overview of the available tools/skills required for Open Science practices. "

Highlights

We asked: "What did you appreciate the most in this Summer School?"

Full participants

[1] "The networking opportunity, hands-on workshop, lively discussion"

[2] "Open my mind and learn the good science practice"

[3] "I really enjoyed this summer school. The topics were well balanced, the tutorials were well organised, the lectures were interesting and broad, the time management was great. The tutors demonstrated know-how from a hands-on-perspective (not purely theoretical). Good breath of subjects covered (technical skills, legislative issues, best practices, practical advice, software tools, databases, websites, communities...). It was intensive but well worth the time. Overall, 5 stars!"

[4] "The fact that it was going very smoothly (from a participant's POV), that it was very motivational, and at places, where it met my needs directly (particularly [workshop names redacted]), the workshops induced a pretty cool flow experience (making me being able to apply the newly acquired skills to my projects immediately). Furthermore, it was very pleasant to spend a week in a good company of lecturers and other participants caring about good science :-)"

[5] "sense of community, openness for discussion, variety of presented topics, excellent time management"

[6] "- hands on workshops - the effort and passion the instructors put into it - interesting guests and topics - hybrid format was implemented very well"

[7] "The comprehensive spectrum of the topics covered. From a technical perspective, it was greatly organised! Thank you!"

[8] "Open conversations and discussions, hybrid format, which helped me to attend the sessions, good coordination, great input"

[9] "I found this workshop to be incredibly relevant and inspiring. [Lecturer's name redacted] really resonated with my experiences and set the tone for the week. My experience in research has been disheartening in the last couple of years – recognizing the issues of research that no one prepares you for. This was inspiring to meet and hear about other researchers having similar experiences. I very much enjoyed many of the talks, especially [Lecturers' names redacted]. I also appreciated, enjoyed, and gained valuable new skills in all of the tutorials! I have to say that this workshop was incredibly well done and I am eager to take back my new knowledge and skills to my working group! Thank you for organising such an event!!!"

[10] "The clear sense of how many people, from different disciplines and fields have similar experiences and willingness to have similar approaches. "

[11] "The atmosphere was really motivating to engage in OS! And overall a pretty nice atmosphere, good and diverse selection of participants from different disciplines"

[12] "- overview over different techniques, good starting point to explore as early career researcher"

[13] "Probably the simple possibility to spend an entire week with a full room of like-minded people"

[14] "The interactions and some of the lectures were outstandingly good "

[15] "Meeting people with similar points of view on the matter of Open Science, discussing it with others, and seeing that it really does matter and it's not just my opinion. "

[16] "Thank you very much for this amazing opportunity! "

Unsolicited emails from full participants

[1] "Thank you very much for organising the summer school!

I am glad to know there is support for those who want to conduct science just right. I found it especially nice to get to know all those with a similar mind, with diverse backgrounds, during this school."

[2] "Thank you again for organising such a wonderful summer school. I learned a lot from the workshop."

[3] "Thank you! I really enjoyed the workshop despite all the hiccups on my end."

[4] "Thank you! It was such a great week. I just reported all the stuff that I learned this week to my supervisor. I learned SO much cool stuff. And the organisation of the whole event was just perfect. So, thank you again!"

[5] "Thank you for the summer school, it was awesome and extremely helpful.

Looking forward to February to get (hopefully) in touch with people from the school once again."

[6] "Thank you very much for the organisation of the summer school. I learned a lot!"

[7] "Big thanks for the great OSC summer school 2023!"

[8] "Thanks for the opportunity to participate in the Summer School."

[9] "Thank you so much for the organisation of last week's summer school, it was a real blast!"

[10] "Thank you so much. It was a great experience for me. I already started lobbying for open science at my university ;)"

Public participants

[1] "I really enjoyed the unique blend of topics covered in one single workshop."

[2] "I did not have the time yet to listen to all the lectures, but so far I like the overall composition of the lectures a lot. So, it's mainly the combination of different topics that I think is inspiring and could be even expanded (more lectures from people outside of the "bubble")."

[3] "- The emphasis on sharing data, materials, codes, and articles appropriately according to the principles of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR), as well as the use of sensitive data anonymization techniques and suitable repositories and licences to maximise the impact of research, allowing others to build upon your work or replicate it. - The guidance provided for reporting results properly and conducting systematic reviews, which contributes to the quality and transparency of research."

[4] "new insights gained by lectures "

[5] "I appreciate the concept and the realisation, plus the speakers. If I was a member of the LMU I definitely also would have joined the practical workshops. That would have been a nice balance to the lectures. Instead, I took part in a self-paced Python tutorial and I worked in my role as data steward."

[6] "Knowledgeable presentations."

[7] "It's great that you organise so many lectures open to everyone. Unfortunately, I didn't have time to participate in many of them, but the content of the lectures was so wide-ranging that there would have been a lot of new things to learn. Thank you very much!"

[8] "Thank you for information about open data."

[9] "getting to know structured info about the topic"

[10] "Hints to Literature and resources"

[11] "This program was a great initiative and opportunity for researchers to learn and to engage with Open Science. It's great the hybrid format allowed people from anywhere in the world to participate. And this is the essence of open science, open to everyone, citizen science! "

[12] "I appreciated the option to join online and especially the fact that the online questions were also considered, it felt like we could participate. Also, having access to the slides at the same time was very useful, and having access to the recording afterwards. "

[13] "It gave a broad overview of what people mean by open science. Plus the fact that it was 5 days gave enough time to get into more details in the different aspects."

[14] "These two lectures were really fantastic!"

Unsolicited email from public participants

[1] "I wanted to thank you and all the team who organised the OSC summer school. This was a great event, with very interesting lectures, and it was awesome to be able to attend online! I really appreciate all the effort you put in to make all of this content available to everyone."

Suggestions for improvement

Finally, we stated: "If you have any suggestions to improve future iterations of such Summer School, please add them here".

Full participants

[1] "I would have loved to have a short introduction of the Open Science Center at the beginning of the Summer School. All in all the organisation was excellent and I loved the hybrid format."

[2] "If it is possible, I hope the open science workshop could be focused on a specific subject. For example, I am in biomedicine, more related to preclinical studies. For me, the data anonymity lecture seems not relevant to me. But I would need more about how to conduct a good experiment on animal experiments, cell experiments, stuff like that. "

[3] "Just one suggestion: Bigger lunch break (2 hours) to allow virtual participants from other time zones to accommodate potential lunch obligations (e.g. feed the kids at their lunch break). Thank you."

[4] "More bananas maybe. Also, I was thinking that if there was a participant that is ok with sharing their project (or outline of thereof), it may be useful to use it as backbone for one workshop where the participants and group leaders could help them to make said project more open. Just an idea though :-)"

[5] "I had the feeling the [workshop names redacted] could rather be offered as lectures"

[6] "There was some redundancy across talks in the first two days. I would also be keen to learn more about lab documentation practices (e.g. <https://psyarxiv.com/rsn5y/>). I really appreciated the [workshop name redacted], as I have been wanting to learn and implement [this] in my practice but never had the time/knew where to look. Something similar that may be useful for non-programmers could be a [workshop suggestion]. Another idea is whether there already exists some repository of these open tutorials and resources for students to search through in order to practise/learn these skills. Sometimes the daunting part is not knowing where to look or how to find it. The [lecture name redacted] was quite relevant with regards to [lecture topic] but a bit dry. For my field, it would have been helpful to have a bit more in how to [implement the practice]. Conceptually, the [workshop name] is a great idea! However, it wasn't as interactive as it possibly

could have been – it felt more like a lecture than a workshop. Perhaps, some preparation before the workshop from the attendees to better create examples and get feedback from the expert. Or working in groups on [the workshop topic]. Likewise, for the What's Next? workshop. This is a great idea to get attendees thinking about the new information but perhaps would have been better suited as the final event. "

[7] "I think we should have more time dedicated to social interactions, so maybe more dinners and open conversation sessions?"

[8] "There could have been more time and room for discussions, especially because we all learned that we cannot as an individual change the way science works, and we are all only small gears in the science machinery. Therefore, discussing the structural problems is very important to develop a deep understanding of the crisis. Lecturers could have been encouraged to stick to the time limits a little bit more. But besides that, it was overall a very pleasant experience!"

[9] "- Diversity is so important, find at least one woman to teach coding (either R, Julia, Quarto, ...) - more hands-on, topics were super interesting but sometimes too theoretical [Lectures names redacted] - too much focus on biology / medicine topics [Lectures names redacted] --> if your summer school is about methods, invite speakers from other fields such as quantitative social scientists, climate modellers, statisticians, ..."

[10] "I think the only real regret/suggestion I would have is that we did not get enough occasions to socialise: everyone was very tired after those very dense days, so it was difficult to do much even in the evening by ourselves. I would suggest maybe very slightly reducing the load, maybe by replacing a couple of lectures by more socialising/networking events"

[11] "I think everything was great except for the lack of engagement in the workshops. And I think the hybrid solution was amazing! "

[12] "There were a lot of repetitions between the lectures"

Public participants

[1] "I think the workshop was very good as it stands. "

[2] "Avoid significant changes between title/abstract and lectures. [Lecture's name redacted] was good, but much more general than advertised. As delivered, his talk was of no use to me (and I skipped the other lecture I had signed up for)."

[3] "I really would have liked to passively follow the workshops online. Thanks a lot for this nicely organised conference!"

[4] "I can't think of any improvements as you have already planned diverse and interesting topics, there has been time for questions, and there have been opportunities to apply theory. It's evident that the organisers have done an excellent job in creating a comprehensive and valuable program. Thank you for your commitment to providing a high-quality educational experience. Thank you for allowing me to participate."

[5] "No suggestion. But thanks for making your lectures accessible for the public."

[6] "Thank you for all your efforts. I appreciate getting the link for the recording lectures. "

[7] "Since I only had time to attend two lectures, I can't say much about the event itself, but in terms of the arrangements, everything went well. It's probably because of my own background, but some of the content seemed very advanced. This was perhaps a little surprising."

[8] "Thank you for supporting the scientists of Ukraine."

[9] "no was really great also the technical support"

[10] "I want to thank the organisers and please keep doing more events like this"

[11] "There was a lot of redundancy in the concepts covered during the different lectures [lectures

names redacted]. Was it intentional as people wouldn't necessarily attend all the lectures?"
[12] "Thanks a lot. Keep up the great work!!"

Conclusions

What could be improved in future events

Content & didactic

- Some lectures could be skipped to avoid redundancy and to **give more time to interactions and open discussions amongst participants**. This should also lead to even higher scores of sense of community / support network, and empowerment to become an ambassador of open research practices.
- Insist with lecturers tasked to provide necessary knowledge (as opposed to being tasked to provide an inspirational speech) that **detailed practical advice** from the perspective of a researcher is more useful and valued than conceptual presentations that do not address implementation challenges.
- Integrate **more engagement during the self-paced tutorials**. Minimally, there could be a wrap-up discussion in the last 15 min of the workshop and/or a live demo. Some further ideas: group check ins, group exercises, a step that requires interacting with the instructor, some easter eggs quiz within the tutorial that appear on the projected screen as participants reach that stage and showcase a skill in a humorous way?
- Make sure to have a **diverse** set of presenters in terms of **gender and disciplines** (i.e. beyond life sciences and medicine, e.g. social scientists).

What to keep for future events

Content & didactic

- Breadth and diversity of topics giving a good overview of open research practices.
- Knowledgeable instructors who provide practical advice.
- Flexibility in navigating workshop material, the very "hands on" approach, and the possibility for directly implementing the skill in participants' projects.

Format

- Inclusivity of both audiences with a well-managed hybrid format.
- Access to materials (slides, tutorials, recordings) during and after the sessions.
- Smooth organisation and time management making people feel motivated.

Annex III - OSC members open science bibliography

Using all published works from our members collected from <https://openalex.org/>, we selected those related to **open science, meta-research, and describing open resources**, by searching for 130+ English keywords in the title and/or abstract and/or journal of publication of the work, and then manually excluding works from this first automatic selection (Table 1).

Table 1. *List of keywords which were found in the OSC members' work titles which were included in the article section of our bibliography, and their number of hits.*

keywords	n
reproducibility	11
open science	9
replicability	8
replication	8
data sharing	6
credibility	5
publication bias	4
metadata	3
open access	3
dataset	2
many analyst	2
methodological research	2
synthetic data	2
academic journal	1
access to data	1
accessibility to complex data	1
code sharing	1
credible research	1
data access	1
database	1
engaging citizen	1
false discovery rate	1
good research practice	1
open data	1
open research	1
open-source	1
p-hacking	1
publication selection bias	1
research data management	1
research protocol	1
sequential hypothesis testing	1
statistical significance	1

This approach may result in bias towards the sciences (as opposed to the humanities), where the lexicon around open science is well established, and where the published literature is mostly in English.

We then created **three bibliographic sections: articles, open source software, and open datasets and material.**

We present the list of articles, open source software, and open datasets and material by field and subfields, as categorised by Open Alex.

1. Articles

1.1. Biology

- Gaona-Gordillo I, Holtmann B, Mouchet A, Hutfluss A, Sánchez-Tójar A & **Dingemans N** (2023). Are animal personality, body condition, physiology and structural size integrated? A comparison of species, populations and sexes, and the value of study replication. *Journal of Animal Ecology*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.13966>
- **Sorbie A**, Jiménez R & Benakis C (2022). Increasing transparency and reproducibility in stroke-microbiota research: a toolbox for microbiota analysis. *iScience*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2022.103998>
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- **Ihle M**, Winney I, Krystalli A & Croucher M (2017). Striving for transparent and credible research: practical guidelines for behavioral ecologists. *Behavioral Ecology*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/beheco/axx003>
- Albl B, Haesner S, Braun-Reichhart C, Streckel E, Renner S, Seeliger F, **Wolf E**, Wanke R & Blutke A (2016). Tissue sampling guides for porcine biomedical models. *Toxicologic Pathology*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192623316631023>
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1.2. Business

- Beniston M, Stoffel M, Harding R, Kernan M, **Ludwig R**, Moors E, Samuels P & Tockner K (2012). Obstacles to data access for research related to climate and water: implications for science and EU policy-making. *Environmental Science & Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2011.12.002>
- Fuchs S & **Sarstedt M** (2010). Is there a tacit acceptance of student samples in marketing and management research? *International Journal of Data Analysis Techniques and Strategies*. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijdots.2010.030011>

1.3. Computer science

1.3.1. General

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1.3.2. Data science

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- **Boulesteix A**, Stierle V & Hapfelmeier A (2015). Publication bias in methodological computational research. *Cancer Informatics*. <https://doi.org/10.4137/cin.s30747>

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